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Artificial Intelligence Applications And Private Secondary Schools Administration In Rivers State, Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

Artificial Intelligence (AI) is increasingly transforming education, with significant implications for secondary school administration traditionally dominated by manual processes. This study examined the relationship between AI applications and the administration of private secondary schools in Rivers State, Nigeria, focusing on efficiency, resource management, and data-driven decision-making. Guided by three research questions and three null hypotheses, the study adopted a correlational research design. The population comprised 8,500 teachers from 1,415 accredited private secondary schools, with a stratified random sample of 850 teachers. Data were collected using validated 4-point rating scale questionnaires, which were validated and reliability coefficients of 0.88 and 0.83 were obtained using Cronbach's Alpha. Pearson Product-Moment Correlation and z-ratio statistics were employed at the 0.05 significance level. Findings revealed a high and significant relationship between assessment/grading, resource optimization, and security management AI applications, and the administration of private secondary schools in Rivers State. Based on these findings, it was concluded that private schools in Rivers State have positioned themselves as forward-thinking institutions committed to leveraging technology, such as AI applications, for administrative excellence. Consequently, it is recommended that private school management or proprietors, through training programs, continuously encourage their teachers to apply AI applications in assessing and grading students to navigate and adjust the level of difficulty and workload they face in grading students to improve individual teacher performance.

Keywords: Artificial Intelligence Applications, Private Secondary Schools, Administration

INTRODUCTION

Artificial Intelligence (AI) is revolutionizing various industries, including education, by offering innovative solutions to traditional problems. In secondary school administration, AI is transforming how schools operate, manage resources, and support students and staff. Secondary education comes after primary school and before higher education. Its main goal is to equip students with knowledge, skills, and attitudes that form the foundation for future careers (FRN, 2014). Some secondary education types, like

vocational schools, are terminal, preparing students for immediate employment. Others prepare students for postsecondary education. Private secondary schools are owned and operated by individuals, though they are overseen by the government, which owns public schools.

In a secondary school, the principal, or school administrator, handles daily operations. This is achieved through administration, which is like the central nervous system of a school: it initiates, directs, controls, and monitors activities. The school administrator's role involves coordinated human efforts to maximize resource utilization and achieve goals. Essentially, administration refers to the responsibilities of the person heading an organization to reach its objectives. School administration involves coordinating human and material resources to effectively accomplish educational goals, with tasks executed through various activities known as administrative processes (Iloya, 2024).

Secondary school administration involves the day-to-day planning and management of school activities to ensure that educational goals are achieved. It includes planning and organising school programmes, coordinating teaching and learning, supervising staff and students, managing school facilities, maintaining discipline, planning the academic calendar, conducting examinations, organising sports and extra-curricular activities, ensuring school security, and maintaining good relationships with the community. Effective administration means arranging school duties clearly, assigning responsibilities to staff, and using proper administrative structures so that the school functions smoothly and achieves its objectives.

Secondary school administration also covers decision-making, budgeting, policy implementation, time-tabling, allocation of duties to teachers, maintenance of facilities, and provision of instructional materials. Recent studies show that effective school administration can be improved through innovations such as Artificial Intelligence (AI). Artificial Intelligence refers to computer-based systems designed to perform tasks that normally require human intelligence, such as thinking, learning, analysing data, and solving problems. AI is now used in many fields, including education, to improve efficiency and accuracy.

In education, AI supports both teaching and administration by automating routine tasks and providing useful information for decision-making. Common AI technologies include machine learning, speech and image recognition, data analysis, and intelligent software systems. These tools help schools manage large amounts of data, identify patterns, and make better administrative decisions. As a result, many schools now use AI tools to improve administration and overall school performance. In secondary school administration, AI is commonly applied in student assessment and grading, resource optimisation, and security management. AI-based assessment systems automatically grade students' work, give feedback, and track learning progress. This helps teachers understand students' performance better and saves time spent on manual grading. Studies have shown that AI-supported grading improves efficiency and supports effective school administration.

AI is also useful in resource optimisation. School administrators are responsible for managing human and material resources, such as teachers, classrooms, and instructional materials. AI systems analyse data on enrolment, class size, and schedules to help administrators allocate resources more effectively. This ensures that available resources are used efficiently to support teaching and learning. Security management is another important area where AI supports school administration. AI-powered security tools help monitor school environments, control access, and detect potential threats. These technologies promote a safe and secure learning environment, which is essential for effective administration and quality education.

Overall, the use of Artificial Intelligence in secondary school administration helps modernise school management, improve efficiency, and enhance decision-making. By adopting AI applications, schools can create safer, more organised, and more effective learning environments. Therefore, this study focused on artificial intelligence applications and the administration of private secondary schools in Rivers State.

Statement of the Problem

The integration of Artificial Intelligence (AI) applications in private secondary schools in Rivers State has the potential to revolutionise key administrative functions, particularly in the areas of assessment and grading of students, resource optimisation, and security management. However, the adoption of these technologies is hindered by challenges such as limited financial resources, insufficient technological infrastructure, and the lack of training and expertise among school administrators and staff. In the context

of student assessment, AI could provide automated grading systems that ensure accuracy, timeliness, and fairness, yet resistance to change and reliance on traditional methods remain barriers to implementation. Resource optimisation, including the effective allocation of teaching staff and materials, could benefit from AI-driven insights, but difficulties in accessing advanced tools pose a significant problem. Similarly, AI-driven security solutions such as facial recognition and automated monitoring could enhance school safety; however, concerns regarding privacy, ethical considerations, and cost impede widespread adoption. Thus, the question troubling the researchers is whether there is a relationship between artificial intelligence applications and the administration of private secondary schools in Rivers State, despite these bottlenecks.

Aim and Objectives of the Study.

This study aimed to investigate the relationship between artificial intelligence applications and private secondary schools administration in Rivers State. Specifically, the study sought to:

1. examine the relationship between assessment/grading AI application and private secondary schools administration in Rivers State.
2. determine the relationship between resource optimisation AI application and private secondary schools administration in Rivers State.
3. find out the relationship between security management AI application and private secondary schools administration in Rivers State.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study.

1. What is the relationship between assessment/grading AI application and private secondary schools administration in Rivers State?
2. What is the relationship between resource optimisation AI application and private secondary schools administration in Rivers State?
3. What is the relationship between security management AI application and private secondary schools administration in Rivers State?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance guided the study

1. There is no significant relationship between assessment/grading AI application and private secondary schools administration in Rivers State.
2. There is no significant relationship between resource optimisation AI application and private secondary schools administration in Rivers State.
3. There is no significant relationship between security management AI application and private secondary schools administration in Rivers State.

METHODOLOGY

This study employed a correlational research design to determine the relationship between the independent variable (artificial intelligence applications) and the dependent variable (administration of private secondary schools). The population comprised 8,500 teachers (3,978 males and 4,522 females) drawn from 1,415 accredited private senior secondary schools in Rivers State. Using a stratified sampling technique, a sample of 850 teachers, representing 10% of the population, was selected, a proportion regarded by Kpee (2015) as adequate for large population. Data were collected using a structured questionnaire made up of two scales: the Artificial Intelligence Applications Scale (AIPS) and the Private Secondary Schools Administration Scale (PSSAS). The instrument contained two sections: Section A sought respondents' demographic information, while Section B addressed research questions one to three. Responses were measured on a 4-point Likert scale of Strongly Agree, Agree, Disagree, and Strongly Disagree. The instrument was validated, and reliability testing using Cronbach's Alpha produced coefficients of 0.88 for AIPS and 0.83 for PSSAS. The researcher, assisted by three trained research assistants, administered 850 copies of the questionnaire, of which 819 were returned and found usable, representing a 96% response rate. Pearson Product-Moment Correlation Coefficient (PPMC) was used to answer the research questions, with correlation values interpreted as very high (0.90–1.00), high (0.70–

0.80), moderate (0.50–0.60), low (0.30–0.40), and very low (below 0.20). The hypotheses were tested using the z-ratio at the 0.05 level of significance.

RESULTS AND ANALYSIS

The results of the analysed data for the research questions and their corresponding hypotheses are presented in tables as shown below.

Research Question 1: *What is the relationship between assessment/grading AI application and private secondary schools administration in Rivers State?*

Table 1: Pearson Product-Moment Correlation (PPMC) Analysis on the Relationship between Assessment/Grading AI Application And Private Secondary Schools Administration in Rivers State

Variable	Σ	Σ^2	n	Df	ΣXY	r	Decision
Assessment/Grading (X)	1613	22031					
			819	817	18429	0.71	High (Positive Relationship)
Private Secondary School Administration (Y)	1723	19442					

Source: Researcher’s Field Result, 2025

The data in Table 1 reveal a correlation coefficient of 0.71. This value is high and positive, indicating that there is a high and positive relationship between the assessment/grading AI application and private secondary schools administration in Rivers State. This implies that an increase in the assessment/grading of students with an AI system leads to a corresponding increase in efficient and effective private secondary school administration in Rivers State.

Research Question 2: *What is the relationship between resource optimisation AI application and private secondary schools administration in Rivers State?*

Table 2: Pearson Product-Moment Correlation (PPMC) Analysis on the Relationship between Resource Optimisation AI Application and Private Secondary Schools Administration in Rivers State

Variable	Σ	Σ^2	N	df	ΣXY	r	Decision
Resource Optimisation (X)	1535	24118					
			819	817	19970	0.73	High (Positive Relationship)
Private Secondary School Administration (Y)	1723	19442					

Source: Researcher’s Field Result, 2025

The data in Table 2 reveal a correlation coefficient of 0.73. This value is high and positive, indicating that there is a high and positive relationship between resource optimisation AI application and private secondary schools administration in Rivers State. This implies that an increase in the use of resource optimisation AI applications leads to a corresponding increase in effective private secondary school administration in Rivers State.

Research Question 3: *What is the relationship between security management AI application and private secondary schools administration in Rivers State?*

Table 3: Pearson Product-Moment Correlation (PPMC) Analysis on the Relationship between Security Management AI Application and Private Secondary Schools Administration in Rivers State

Variable	Σ	Σ^2	N	df	ΣXY	r	Decision
Security Management (X)	1274	16732					
			819	817	15166	0.70	High (Positive Relationship)
Secondary School Administration (Y)	1723	19442					

Source: Researcher's Field Result, 2025

The data in Table 3 reveal a correlation coefficient of 0.70. This value is high and positive, indicating that there is a high and positive relationship between security management AI applications and private secondary schools administration in Rivers State. This implies that an increase in artificial intelligence applications in enhancing security leads to a corresponding increase in private secondary school administration in Rivers State.

Test of Hypothesis

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant relationship between assessment/grading AI application and private secondary schools administration in Rivers State.

Table 4: z-ratio on the Relationship between Assessment/Grading AI Application and Private Secondary Schools Administration in Rivers State

Variable	Σ	Σ^2	N	df	ΣXY	r	z-ratio	z-crit	Decision
Assessment/Grading (X)	1613	22031							
			819	817	18429	0.71	21.03	1.96	Failed to Accept H_0 (Significant)
Private Secondary School Administration (Y)	1723	19442							

Source: Researcher's Field Result, 2025

Data in Table 4 reveal that a high positive relationship exists between assessment/grading AI application and private secondary schools administration in Rivers State. To establish the significance of the relationship, the z-ratio was computed and an index of 21.03 was obtained. This was compared to the critical z-score of 1.96 at the 0.05 level of significance with a degree of freedom of 817, indicating that there is a significant positive relationship between assessment/grading AI application and private secondary schools administration in Rivers State (calculated $z = 21.03 > \text{critical } z = 1.96$ at $p < 0.05$ and $df = 817$). Therefore, the null hypothesis of no significant relationship between assessment/grading AI application and private secondary schools administration in Rivers State is rejected.

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant relationship between resource optimisation AI application and private secondary schools administration in Rivers State.

Table 5: z-ratio on The Relationship between Resource Optimisation AI Application and Private Secondary Schools Administration in Rivers State

Variable	Σ	Σ^2	N	Df	ΣXY	r	z-ratio	z-crit	Decision
Resource Optimisation (X)	1535	24118							
			819	817	19970	0.73	25.17	1.96	Failed to Accept Ho ₂ (Significant)
Private Secondary School Administration (Y)	1723	19442							

Source: Researcher's Field Result, 2025

Data in Table 5 reveal that a high positive relationship exists between resource optimisation AI application and private secondary schools administration in Rivers State. To establish the significance of the relationship, the z-ratio was computed and an index of 25.17 was obtained. This was compared to the critical z-score of 1.96 at the 0.05 level of significance with a degree of freedom of 817, indicating that there is a significant positive relationship between resource optimisation AI application and private secondary schools administration in Rivers State (calculated $z = 25.17 > \text{critical } z = 1.96$ at $p < 0.05$ and $df = 817$). Therefore, the null hypothesis of no significant relationship between resource optimisation AI application and private secondary schools administration in Rivers State is rejected.

Hypothesis 3: There is no significant relationship between security management AI application and private secondary schools administration in Rivers State.

Table 6: z-ratio on the Relationship between Security Management AI Application and Private Secondary Schools Administration in Rivers State

Variable	Σ	Σ^2	N	Df	ΣXY	r	z-ratio	z-crit	Decision
Security Management (X)	1274	16732							
			819	817	15166	0.70	19.23	1.96	Failed to Accept Ho ₄ (Significant)
Secondary School Administration (Y)	1723	19442							

Source: Researcher's Field Result, 2025

Data in Table 6 reveal that a high positive relationship exists between security management AI application and private secondary schools administration in Rivers State. To establish the significance of the relationship, the z-ratio was computed and an index of 19.23 was obtained. This was compared to the critical z-score of 1.96 at the 0.05 level of significance with a degree of freedom of 817, indicating that there is a significant positive relationship between security management AI application and private secondary schools administration in Rivers State (calculated $z = 19.23 > \text{critical } z = 1.96$ at $p < 0.05$ and $df = 817$). Therefore, the null hypothesis of no significant relationship between security management AI application and private secondary schools administration in Rivers State is rejected.

df = 817). Therefore, the null hypothesis of no significant relationship between security management AI application and private secondary schools administration in Rivers State is rejected.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The first finding of the study revealed that there is high and positive relationship between assessment/grading AI application and private secondary schools administration in Rivers State. A corresponding hypothesis tested established a significant positive relationship between assessment/grading AI application and private secondary schools administration in Rivers State. These findings corroborate Oztok and Zingaro (2019), Bryant (2020), Bell, et al (2022) whose empirical studies showed that there is a positive and significant relationship between artificial intelligence application in grading of students and secondary school administration goal achievement. To the scholars, assessment/Grading AI application is used to improve the efficiency of grading and assessment of students in order to facilitate teacher work activities. A possible explanation for these may be in fact that quite very recently, private schools have had to take advantage of ICT means like AI in assessing and grading of students.

The second finding of the study showed that there is high and positive relationship between resource optimisation AI application and private secondary schools administration in Rivers State. Also, the corresponding hypothesis tested establishes a significant positive relationship between resource optimisation AI application and private secondary schools administration in Rivers State. These findings are in agreement with the studies of Ogunode and Gregory (2023), AFSA (2022), Ogunode, et al (2021) whose empirical works averred that there is a correlation between resource optimisation AI application and private secondary schools administration in Rivers State. These may further be explained due to the fact that private school managers or administrators and other members have come to the realisation that resource optimisation AI application remains a tool in the achievement of effective private secondary school administration.

The third finding of the study showed that there is high and positive relationship between security management AI application and private secondary schools administration in Rivers State. Similarly, the corresponding hypothesis tested establishes a significant positive relationship between security management AI application and private secondary schools administration in Rivers State. These findings are in line with Duncanson and Achilles (2019), Gichuhi, et al (2019), Muyiwa (2021), AFSA (2022), Gill and Spriggs (2022) whose studies observed that Security AI applications or gadgets can contribute toward enhancing school security management for achievement of secondary school administration. A possible explanation to these finding is the fact that many private schools are making use of AI-driven security management application, such as facial recognition and automated monitoring to enhance security in schools by school management to monitor the activities that students and staff engage in within the school environment, thereby promoting effective administrative system.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, private schools in Rivers State have positioned themselves as forward-thinking institutions committed to leveraging technology like AI applications for administrative excellence, considering that there is a high and significant relationship between assessment/grading, resource optimisation, security management, AI applications and private secondary schools administration in Rivers State.

RECOMMENDATIONS

In light of the findings and conclusions of the study, the following are recommended:

1. Private school management or proprietors, through training programmes, should continuously encourage their teachers to apply artificial intelligence applications in assessing and grading students to navigate and adjust the level of difficulty and workload they face in assessing/grading of students to improve individual teacher performance.

2. Private school management should always carry out training and retraining programmes for their managers or administrators as well as their staff, to ensure full use of resource optimisation AI applications in school administrative activities.
3. The government should encourage private schools through proper supervision to continue to utilise security management AI applications in ensuring the security and safety of students and staff.

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